

As on 16-08-2019, the following data entry procedures are recommended in order to add record of new crop into the knowledge base system. The crops records were mainly obtained from Ecocrop database. The records are increasing from time to time as data collection efforts continue.

1. Prior to data entry, one should know the following:
 - 'Crop Records' is the main table for recording the specific name, common name and names of taxon ranks exist for an individual organism.
 - Procedures of data entry into the database (how to enter the data into the table); user will be trained for the data entry before entering data.
2. IMPORTANT: Prior to data entry, one has to ensure that the crop data that is going to be entered does not exist in record of the database.
3. There are 8 fields to be entered, seven of them are meant to be compulsory for every record.

3.1 Crop ID (Auto-generated)

- This is referring to the unique ID of the record.

3.2 Name (Compulsory)

- This is referring to the common name which belongs to a specific crop subspecies, variety, cultivar or landrace.
- One usually could find the name by searching using the whole name of an organism's scientific name.
- The name must be **UNIQUE** to other records. Search the name to be created. Ensure there is **NO** previous record which has used the name to be created.
- In case where a unique name cannot be created, locate scientific name (binomial name) in brackets next to the genus common name. E.g. Needle Grass (*Stipa barbata*)
- It is recommended to use the common name from NCBI Taxonomy (<https://www.ncbi.nlm.nih.gov/taxonomy>).
- In cases where there are multiple common names for the crop species, choose the name which has the highest frequency in the search engine (Google).
- This might be difficult to certain crops which have huge varieties. In case where the name could not be found widely on the net, one could try to find the most probable matched name in the reliable research article.

3.2.1 Name of a subspecies

- In case where the specific name for a subspecies is not found, write 'var. variety name' after the common name. E.g. Long Beans 'subsp. *Sesquipedalis*'

3.2.2 Name of a variety

- In case where the specific name for a variety is not found, write 'subsp. subspecies name' after the common name. E.g. Capsicum 'var. *accuminatum*'

3.2.3 Name of a cultivar and landrace

- A cultivar would usually have its own name. The name is recorded in single quotation marks i.e. 'cultivar name'. E.g. Adzuki Bean 'Kuro-shozu'
- A landrace would usually have its own name. The name is recorded in single quotation marks in the database i.e. 'landrace name'. E.g. Bambara Groundnut 'Songkhla'

3.2.4 Name of a crop with lower taxa

- A crop with specific lower taxa from subspecies or variety would usually have its own name. This is common for a species with huge varieties e.g. *Brassica rapa*.

3.2.5 Name of a genotype/line/accession/other

- The name of a genotype/line/accession usually would be recorded after the common name. E.g. Bambara Groundnut 20ACC118CIV-B
- Other uncommon tag of a crop should be discussed among data managers before being entered into the database.

3.3 Scientific Name (Compulsory)

- This is referring to the unique binomial name given to a specific crop. This comprises combination of Genus and Single specific epithet. E.g. *Vigna subterranea*
- Add subspecies, variety, cultivar or landrace, infraspecific name (see section below).
- It is recommended to use the scientific name from NCBI Taxonomy.
- In case where the crop does not exist in NCBI Taxonomy database, one could find the scientific name in The Plant List (<http://www.theplantlist.org>) or Integrated Taxonomic Information System (<https://www.itis.gov>) databases.
- This might be difficult to certain crops which have huge variety. In case where the name could not be found widely on the net, one could try to find the most probable matched name in the reliable research article.
- The record in database cannot be italicised due to software system rule.

3.3.1 Scientific name with subspecies name

- Write 'subsp.' after the species name e.g. *Digitaria eriantha* subsp. *eriantha*

3.3.2 Scientific name with variety name

- Write 'var.' after the species name e.g. *Brassica rapa* var. *parachinensis*

3.3.3 Scientific name with cultivar name

- Write the cultivar name in single quotation marks after the scientific name. E.g. *Persea americana* 'Hass'

3.3.4 Scientific name of a landrace

- Write the landrace name in single quotation marks after the scientific name. E.g. *Vigna subterranea* 'Songkhla'

3.3.5 Scientific name with other lower taxa name

- The name shall follow the reliable source mentioning the lower taxa name. E.g. Green Cabbage is *Brassica oleracea* var. *capitata* subgroup *alba*.

3.3.6 Scientific name of a genotype/line/accession/other

- The name shall follow the reliable source mentioning the scientific name. In the database, the scientific name is recorded as it is without any addition of the specific genotype/line/accession name. E.g. Bambara Groundnut 20ACC118CIV-B scientific name is recorded as *Vigna subterranea*.

3.4 Family Name (Compulsory)

- This is referring to the larger subgroup of the organism which is positioned between Order and Genus in the taxonomy ranking.
- It is recommended to use the taxon name from NCBI Taxonomy.
- There might be alternative names exist for a family name. The alternative names should be recorded in the 'Notes'.
- The family name shall be recorded in an option table 'Opt Family' and the record shall be entered as ID chosen by the data manager (in the database the field will show a drop-down menu for selection).
- In order to add the family name record, ensure there is **NO** previous record of the same family name as the record must be **UNIQUE**.

3.5 Intraspecific Category

- This is to indicate the taxa rank below species.

3.6 Synonyms

- This is referring to the alternative binomial name given to a specific crop species, subspecies, variety, cultivar or landrace.
- Names are entered in open-ended format given the next name is followed after a comma and a space.

3.7 Crop Type (Compulsory)

- This is to indicate the type of crop which produces yield within a year or more i.e. temporary/permanent/not specified (Food and Agriculture Organization, 2011).

3.8 Notes

- This field is to store other information which is related to the crop itself.

3.9 Metadata ID (Compulsory)

Draft status

- This field is to link the record to its metadata.
- One MUST create a Metadata record in 'Metadata' table before entering Metadata ID.

References:

- International Code of Nomenclature for algae, fungi, and plants (Shenzhen Code) (2017). CHAPTER I - TAXA AND THEIR RANKS ARTICLE 4. Retrieved from https://www.iapt-taxon.org/nomen/pages/main/art_4.html
- Food and Agriculture Organization (2011). Tree crops - Guidelines for estimating area data. Retrieved from [http://www.fao.org/fileadmin/templates/ess/ess_test_folder/documents/Production trade/definitions/Tree_crops_guidelines_for_estaimating_area.doc](http://www.fao.org/fileadmin/templates/ess/ess_test_folder/documents/Production_trade/definitions/Tree_crops_guidelines_for_estaimating_area.doc)